

PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY OF GENERAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8044489>

Abstract. *The content of this article is to determine the essence of general cultural competence of a future teacher as an integral component of his pedagogical culture, to develop a conceptual model of the development of general cultural competence of a future teacher at the post-high school education stage, and to determine the criteria and indicators for evaluating general cultural competence as one of the success factors in pedagogical activity. made up of ideas, thoughts, rules.*

Keywords: *competence, education and culture, pedagogical category.*

The content of this part is to determine the essence of the general cultural competence of the future teacher as an integral component of his pedagogical culture, to develop a conceptual model of the development of the general cultural competence of the future teacher at the post-high school education stage, and to determine the criteria and indicators for evaluating the general cultural competence as one of the success factors in pedagogical activity. made up of ideas, thoughts, rules.

The difference in the philosophical and methodological approaches of the future teachers of these three subjects to this problem was also revealed in the answers to the third question of the questionnaire: "In your opinion, which qualities of a future teacher are considered the most important for his general culture? (put the answers in order of decreasing importance):

- extensive and thorough reading of literature and knowledge of your country and international art;

- Knowledge of Russian and world history;
- knowledge of foreign languages;
- to know the basics of natural and mathematical sciences;
- philosophical knowledge;
- behavioral culture.
- speech culture.
- know their region;
- any other answers.

Only 4% of future teachers of mathematics believe that "knowing the basics of natural and mathematical sciences is the last important indicator of the general culture of a future teacher, and 10% and 19% put it in the second and third place, respectively. For comparison, 44% of future teachers of physics and 54% of future teachers of chemistry put this indicator in the last place.

At this point, we should emphasize the fact that the future teachers of mathematics generally underestimate the role of philosophical knowledge in the general culture of the future teacher. When answering the third question, only 24% of them put this indicator in one of the first three places: 5% - in the first place, 7% - in the second place, 12% - in the third place. In comparison, 53% of prospective chemistry teachers rated knowledge of philosophy as one of the three most important things for the general culture.

How do you understand the meaning of the phrase “Pedagogical culture of the future teacher?” the answers to the question deserve interest 78% of respondents to some extent connect the future teacher’s pedagogical culture with his general culture.

In the most standard answers, we give an example: “Pedagogical culture of the future teacher is respect for the personality of the student, the general culture of the future teacher and knowledge of child psychology”. “The pedagogical culture of the future teacher is his general culture and pedagogical professionalism”, “The pedagogical culture of the future teacher is excellent knowledge of science plus general culture”, et al.

“Trying to avoid traditional criticisms for the narrowness and simplicity of the approach to the studied problem, it is self-evident that some authors call it almost impossible for a future teacher to have a high pedagogical culture: the teacher will have creative potential and the whole world’s cultural-historical experience will be embodied in him” (28, 66-6.).

Undoubtedly, the pedagogue scientist A.S.Makarenko had a high pedagogical culture, was well-educated, well-educated, but in 1922, when he became an old man, he wrote about his cultural and historical knowledge: “... arithmetic, geometry, algebra, trigonometry and physics gave me only the pre-revolutionary institute of future teachers is familiar within the course. < ... > My knowledge of philosophy is very unsystematic. I have read Locke, Critique of Pure Reason, Schopenhauer, Stirner, Nietzsche and Bergson...” (97, 9-10 б.). A.S. Even taking into account Makarenko’s personal modesty and the large amount of philosophical knowledge contained in the works of the authors he represented, it is difficult to call the great pedagogue “the center of the world’s cultural and historical experience”. Teachers V.A.Sukhomlinsky and A.A.Zakharenko and S.N.Lisenkova, E.N.Ilin, R.G.Khazankin it is unlikely that and other famous pedagogues can claim this title. The cited examples clearly show that the last of the conditions stated by the authors is not only unattainable, but also not necessary. “No future teacher can be universal and therefore cannot be an abstract embodiment of all qualities” (155, 113-6.). At the same time, it is self-evident that one cannot have a high pedagogical culture without being educated, well-educated, scientific, and erudite.

The analysis of the literature carried out by us shows that the concept of pedagogical culture of a future teacher in pedagogy is usually “pedagogical skill” and “pedagogical technique” (7, 33-б.) indicates that it is interconnected with such concepts. Scientist N.V.Kuzmina defines the skills of a future teacher as “the highest level of pedagogical activity at which a pedagogue achieves optimal results in the allotted time” (85, 30-б.) or “the synthesis of scientific knowledge, methodical art qualifications and skills and personal qualities and characteristics of the future teacher” (85, 30 б.) describes as Scientists of the Poltava Pedagogical Institute see the basis of pedagogical skill in the qualities of the future teacher that contribute to the success of the pedagogical activity. In this, they consider skill as a set of characteristics of a person that provides a high level of independent organization of professional activity (118, 10-б.). A.I. Shcherbakov develops the skills of the future teacher, which provides a high level of information interaction between the future teacher and students; understands it as a theoretically based and justified in practice, proven pedagogical work, action, actions and operations (182, p. 15).

When comparing the concepts of pedagogical culture and pedagogical skills, it should be noted that the concept of pedagogical culture is broader and more multifaceted. “Pedagogical skill is only one of the aspects of pedagogical culture related to the acquisition of specific skills and

abilities” (7, 34 б.). Perhaps, the skill of the future teacher can be interpreted as the level of mastery of the components of the pedagogical culture that the future teacher has achieved.

In pedagogy, the term “pedagogical technique” is usually understood as a set of skills that help future teachers to achieve high results in everyday practical work: “...pedagogical technique” means the optimal and creative behavior of a future teacher in any pedagogical situation and with children a set of skills that help effective interaction is understood” (162, 7). It should also be noted that the modern interpretation of the term “pedagogical technique” has a direct similarity with the understanding of technique in some other areas of human activity, in particular, in art and sports.

The American psychologist D. According to Holland’s classification, the teaching profession belongs to the social type (p. 15, 56). T.E. Kovina and A.P. Scholars such as Shapkina “pedagogical profession represents a social mechanism created by society to ensure the need to transfer social experience from older generations to young people in a direct and goal-oriented manner...” (78, 7 б.). Scientists such as Yu.V.Senko and V.E. Tamarin among the three main factors determining the effectiveness of the educational process are “culture personified, embodied in the future teacher (social experience, including pedagogical experience)” (140, 73-б.). V.L.Benin noted, “the pedagogue is not free in his educational opportunities. At the basis of the specific forms and methods of his professional activity there is a specific, historically formed socio-cultural complex” (8, 6-б.). B.S. Gershunsky “a future teacher is not only a person who has received a special pedagogical education, but also a person who always feels the urgency of social problems, performs the most important social function, ensures the connection of times and the succession of generations...” (38, 3 б.). The role of the social component in the pedagogical culture of the future teacher was studied by scientist L.S.Vygotsky: It was clearly defined by “From a scientific point of view, the future teacher is only the organizer of the social learning environment, the regulator-regulator and supervisor of his interaction with each student” (29, 192 б.). B.M. Bim-Bad and A.V. According to Petrovsky: “...education can be considered as a purposeful, pedagogically organized and planned socialization of a person... “ (11, 3 б.).

Within the framework of our research, “in the pedagogy and psychology of our country, there are age-old traditions of establishing various relations between socialization and education” (11. 3 б.). “Throughout the centuries, the main system-forming function of education in every society has been to convey the content of social culture to young generations for its reproduction and development”. Analyzing the problems of the formation of a teacher’s personality, scientist V.I.Filippova in particular emphasizes the following: “The future social culture is of great professional importance for a teacher, professional culture reflects his level of professional skill” (169, 59-б.). Although we generally agree with the author’s view, there are some changes to it as appropriate to include we know In our opinion, it is more correct to assume that social culture is not a reflection of the skills of the future teacher, but rather the pedagogical culture of the future teacher, which directly or indirectly affects the success of the professional activity of the future teacher. According to scientist L.I.Novikova, “the task of teachers is to teach children to:

- to be able to see the positive and negative aspects of the environment and to treat them adequately.
- to feel that he belongs to the environment and his responsibility for it:
- to improve the environment, to feel the need to change it according to the laws of humanity and beauty;...” (113, 77 б.).

In the research conducted on the problems of pedagogical culture in recent years, it is emphasized that the concept of pedagogical culture “is concretized in the concepts” of “pedagogical activity culture”, “pedagogical communication culture”, “culture of the future teacher”, which reveal the diversity of the content and structure of this concept (66, 16 б.). According to V.V.Tarasov’s expression, “the objective unity of the general, socio-ethical and professional development of the future teacher’s personality actualizes and renews the formation of his pedagogical culture” (158, 36-6.).

Thus, the content of the concept of pedagogical culture of a future teacher should include indicators that describe his social culture: communication, cooperation with colleagues, positive self-perception, resistance to ideological influence, etc.

So, pedagogical culture is the combination of three main components that are closely related and interpenetrating each other, considered as a combination of: the culture of the future teacher’s professional activity, the general culture of the future teacher and his social culture.

- the area where the culture of professional activity and the general culture coincide and intersect;

- the area where the culture of professional activity and social culture coincide and intersect;

- an area where general culture and social cultures overlap and intersect;

- the area where the culture of professional activity, general and social cultures overlap and intersect:

Here, we understand the professional culture of a future teacher as the culture of his pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical work (methodological culture, mastery of pedagogical techniques, pedagogical creativity, mastery of science teaching methods, pedagogical manners, ethics, etc.). The general culture of the future teacher is manifested in the qualities that serve as indicators of the person's general cultural worldview (thorough study of literature, knowledge of the world and our country's art, etc.). Social culture is determined by the level of social maturity of a person and the qualities mentioned above.

The interpenetration and passing of the structural parts is expressed in the fact that many indicators are common to two of them, and can be considered as belonging to all three basic structural forms of pedagogical culture. For example, the culture of speech is a common indicator of the culture of professional activity and general culture, the culture of setting goals and According to K.M.Levitan’s expression, “.. there was nothing but the culture of human interaction”. Pedagogical culture of communication - culture of professional activity and social culture common, behavioral culture, with colleagues able to work cooperatively ability and possession of erudition in socio-political issues - common to general and social cultures. Qualities that describe the moral character of the future teacher (his conscientiousness, tolerance, open-mindedness, persistence in keeping his word, etc.), it is self-evident that it is necessary to study all three components.

Interrelationship and mutual location of the elements that make up the three main parts of pedagogical culture different specialties? It should be noted that the specialty is different for future teachers. For example, for a future teacher of mathematics, knowing them will be an element of both the general culture and the culture of professional activity at the same time. It is self-evident that the same can be said of his extensive and thorough reading of the literature when applied to the future teacher of physics.

According to the initial plan and idea of the research, one of the integral components of the future teacher's pedagogical culture, belonging to its three main components at the same time, is his general cultural competence.

In the traditional understanding, the term "competence" is interpreted as "the range of issues in which a certain person has knowledge, information and experience". Taking this into account and in accordance with the purpose and hypothesis of the research, we understand the general cultural competence of the future teacher as a personal and professional characteristic that shows his readiness and readiness to introduce students to the cultural context of the subject being taught.

The universal competence of the future teacher is a concept whose essence cannot be revealed when studying it in any aspect (professional activity, universal outlook, scientific knowledge, etc.). In the recommended interpretation, universal competence serves as an integrative professional and personal characteristic of a future teacher, which requires a multifaceted approach to its study.

REFERENCES

1. Сухомлинский В. А. Рождение гражданина. Перевод с украинского. - М.: Изд-во ЦК ВЛКСМ "Молодая гвардия", 1971.-336 с.
2. Бенин В. Л. Педагогическая культура: ее содержание и специфика /Башк. пед. ин-т. - Уфа, 1994.
3. Кузьмина Н. В. Очерки психологии труда учителя. Психологическая структура деятельности учителя и формирование его личности. - Л.: Изд-во ЛГУ, 1967.- 184 с
4. Основы педагогического мастерства. Учебное пособие для педагогических специальных высших учебных заведений /Под ред. И. А. Зязюна. - М.: Просвещение, 1989. - 302 с.
5. Турчанинова Ю. И. Педагогическая техника и мастерство учителя: В кн. Учителю о педагогической технике /Под ред. Л. И. Рувинского. - М.: Педагогика 1987. - 160 с., с. 4-14.
6. Ковина Т. Е., Шапкина А. П. Аттестация педагогических и руководящих работников государственных и муниципальных образовательных учреждений в контексте педагогической культуры. - СПб: СПб. ун-т педагогического мастерства, 1996. - 38 с.
7. Сенько Ю. В., Тамарин В. Э. Обучение и жизненный познавательный опыт учащихся. - М.: Знание, 1989. - 80 с. - (Новое в жизни, науке, технике. Сер. "Педагогика и психология", № 12).
8. Бенин В. Л. Теоретико-методологические основы формирования и развития педагогической культуры. Автореф. дис. ... докт. пед. наук. - Екатеринбург: УГПТУ, 1996. - 32 с.
9. Гершунский Б. С. Философия образования. - М.: Московский психолого-социальный институт, Флинта, 1998. - 432 с.
10. Воробьев Н. Е., Суханцева В. К., Иванова Т. В. О педагогической культуре будущего учителя //Педагогика, 1992, № 1-2, с. 66-70.
11. Макаренко А. С. Заявление в Центральный институт организаторов народного просвещения. Пед. соч. в 8 т. - М., 1983. - Т. 1. - С. 8-11.

12. Выготский Л. С. Предисловие к русскому переводу книги Э. Торндайка «Принципы обучения, основанные на психологии». Собр. соч. в 6 т. - М.: Педагогика, 1982. - Т. 1. - с. 176-195.
13. Бим-Бад Б. М., Петровский А. В. Образование в контексте со-циализации //Педагогика, 1996, № 1, с. 3-8.
14. Филиппова В. И. Культура и мировоззрение учителя //Педагогика, 1992, № 3-4, с. 58-63.
15. Новикова Л. И. Школа и среда. - М.: Знание, 1985. - 80 с. - (Новое в жизни, науке, технике. Сер. "Педагогика и психология", № 8.)
16. Исаев И. Ф. Теоретические основы формирования профессионально-педагогической культуры преподавателя высшей школы. Автореф. дис.... докт. пед. наук. - М.: 1993. - 33 с.
17. Тарасов В. В. Региональная система педагогического образования учителя: Теоретические подходы, опыт и перспективы развития. - Пенза, 1997.-216 с.
18. Левитан К. М. Личность педагога: Становление и развитие. - Саратов: Изд-во Саратовского ун-та, 1990. - 168 с.